

Implant rehabilitation with direct sinus lift – A case report

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Abstract

For the management of posterior edentulous areas sinus lift has become a popular modality. The high success rates and minimal complications associated with the procedure make it a highly predictable treatment option. The article was aimed to describe a case of direct sinus lift with implant placement.

Keywords: direct sinus lift, sinus augmentation, sinus floor elevation, posterior dental implants.

Introduction

Implant rehabilitation can be complicated due to insufficient bone, especially in the posterior maxilla. Long-term tooth loss is often accompanied by pneumatization of the sinus and resorption of alveolar bone. (1) With no distal support, the use of short implants or removable dentures is the only available option. Implants having lengths more than 10-12 mm have higher

success rates compared to shorter implants. (2) Thus, shorter implants or removable dentures both cannot provide a long-term solution to the patient. To deal with these issues alternative treatment modality known as maxillary sinus lift was developed. The positive outcome of the procedure has made it more acceptable compared to shorter implants. (3, 4)

A sinus lift is a procedure wherein the Schneiderian membrane is separated and lifted from the sinus wall. A graft material is then inserted below the lifted membrane. (5) This surgical procedure can be done as a single-stage or two-stage procedure. The single stage involves sinus floor augmentation with implant placement. The approach for sinus augmentation can be either lateral (Direct) or crestal (Indirect). (6)

Direct approach also known as lateral window approach has several advantages. (7) It was first described by Tatum. (8) The direct approach provides for good access and visualization, and it can be done universally for all cases of sinus lift. An indirect approach can only be performed if the residual height is more than 6 mm. Also, the bone gain achieved by the indirect approach is comparatively less than a direct approach. (2, 9, 10) This case report describes a case that was managed with direct sinus lift with immediate implant placement.

Case report

A 29-year-old female patient reported to the outpatient section in the Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery, Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College, Nagpur. After radiographic investigations, insufficient bone was observed in the maxillary first molar region. (Figure 1) Considering the age of the patient and other clinical parameters, implant rehabilitation was planned with sinus floor augmentation. Blood investigations were performed. Pre-surgical

surgical protocol was followed. Informed consent was taken from the patient after explaining the treatment as well as other alternatives.

The surgery was performed under local anesthesia (2% lignocaine, 1:80,000 adrenaline). After achieving anesthesia, an incision was made with #15 no blade extending from the second premolar to the second molar. Vertical releasing incision was given and full thickness flap was reflected. (Figure 2) The lateral window was marked on the lateral surface and quadrilateral osteotomy was performed. (Figure 3) Round carbide bur was used to trace the window and eventually, the bone fragment was fractured from the surrounding bone. (Figure 4) The membrane was then gradually lifted from the wall of the sinus. (Figure 5) The membrane was checked during respiration for tear or perforation. Graft material (Xenograft) was placed below the membrane. Osteotomy was performed for implant placement and an implant of size diameter 5 and length 11.5mm (Noris) was inserted. (Figure 6) A collagen membrane was placed and the surgical site was closed with sutures. (Figure 7) After 6 months the bone gain was evaluated and gingival former was placed. (Figure 8) An open tray impression was made in addition to silicone and a screw-retained prosthesis was delivered. (Figure 9, 10) No surgical or prosthetic complications were encountered during the procedure. The implant showed successful integration.

Discussion

The loss of molar due to caries or periodontal problems is not uncommon. In the current era of dentistry, the replacement of a single tooth with a dental implant is considered the best treatment. However, tooth replacement in the posterior maxilla is challenging due to the limited bone volume as well as the poor quality of existing bone. (1, 11, 12) Sinus lift procedure encounters

this problem of insufficient bone and facilitates placement of implant even in a highly pneumatized sinus. Few studies have compared bone gain in direct and indirect approaches. (2, 13) They concluded that direct sinus lift procedures favor significant gain in bone compared to the indirect approach. The indirect procedure however is less invasive and therefore has less post-op pain and soft tissue swelling. (2, 14, 15)

Successful implant placement can be performed with this lateral window technique as seen in this case. The procedure can be mastered by enhancing knowledge of maxillary anatomy and with practice. This procedure benefits the patients by providing a long-term solution compared to removable dentures or short implants. One-stage placement reduces the duration of overall treatment and avoids a need for a second surgery making the experience more comfortable for the patient. The use of xenograft material and resorbable collagen membranes also increases the effectiveness of the procedure. (5)

Conclusion

One-stage direct sinus lift provides a successful and predictable treatment option for cases with insufficient bone and sinus pneumatization. It is also a cost-effective procedure and has minimal complication rates. Xenograft and collagen membranes help to enhance the results of the sinus lift. The one-stage protocol makes the treatment more acceptable and patient-friendly.

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Figure 1: Pre-operative OPG

Figure 2: Flap reflection and marking done for lateral window

Figure 3: Quadrilateral osteotomy

Figure 4: Schneiderian membrane through the created lateral window

Figure 5: Sinus membrane separation

Figure 6: Xenograft and Implant placed

Figure 7: Flap closed

Figure 8: Six months post-op OPG

Figure 9: Open tray impression

Figure 10: Final screw-retained prosthesis